

Decentralized treatment of greywater with intensified Nature-based solutions for reuse in public schools: an innovative approach in Luxembourg

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Abstract

On-site greywater separation allows for water reuse at the source, cutting distribution costs and infrastructure needs. The use of intensified nature-based solutions in households responds to the need for efficient, low cost and sustainable technology. Preliminary results of a pilot plant installed at the international school Edward Steichen situated in the North of Luxembourg show the high quality of the treated water with pathogen indicators compliant with the standards for water reuse and offer a suitable case study to favour the transition and implement new regulations.

Keywords

Biochar, Constructed wetlands, Greywater, water reuse

INTRODUCTION

Water stress indicators have been widely used over the last 20 years to assess ecosystem vulnerability to water scarcity. Population and economic growth have driven higher freshwater consumption for agriculture, industry, and households, while climate change has lowered groundwater replenishment, complicating compliance with the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC). This has led Member States to adopt cross-sectoral measures.

Although Luxembourg has been seen as water-abundant, limits on consumptive use were already set in 2008 (*The Water Act*). Currently, 57% of its annual water use (45 million m³ in 2022) comes from groundwater, with the remaining 43% sourced from the Esch-sur-Sûre reservoir located in the North with 2/3 of its catchment in Belgium. Forecasts predict that withdrawals will equal freshwater replenishment by 2035, highlighting the need for responsible use. Luxembourgish households consume 140 litres per day per capita, accounting for 60% of water use, followed by industry (23%) and agriculture (7%). While industrial consumption is lower than in other Member States due to the steel industry's decline, agricultural use is expected to grow with a focus on local food production. Household consumption has risen by 1.35% annually over 15 years, reflecting demographic growth and cross-border commuters. This project, funded by Luxembourg's water agency, aims to save potable water by reusing light greywater (e.g., from showers) for non-drinking purposes like toilet flushing. There are key challenges including legal standards, cost, public acceptance, and liability, which hinder its adoption in the construction sector. The optimization of the technology efficiency is addressed to broaden its application: a novel substrate to better remove pollutants, support plant growth and serve as a medium for adsorption and biodegradation of most recalcitrant compounds such as personal care products. A biochar produced from plant residues in a circular economy perspective and activated biologically by fermentation is tested as an admixture to non-conventional sand. This addition provides unique support for pollutant transformation and removal. The good performance of this biochar has already been confirmed in previous projects as a polishing step of treated urban wastewater effluents for the removal of emerging pollutants, such as pharmaceuticals (Brunhoferova et al., 2021; Venditti et al., 2022). In addition, previous results from a laboratory scale study have already highlighted this material as a promising alternative when mixed with sand for the removal of personal care products from greywater (Muniz Sacco et al., 2024). Therefore, this project is a step forward to test this material on a pilot scale for greywater treatment under real conditions with the ultimate scope to prove and standardize the technology looking at pathogen removal (disinfection process), operational and maintenance issues, space requirements, and real-time control.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pilot plant

A Nature-based Solution (NbS) will be tested at the international school Edward Steichen (with circa 741 students in 2021-2022) situated in the North of Luxembourg at the municipality of Clervaux. The pilot plant is located in the swimming pool basement, on the side of an already existing facility devoted to the treatment of the light greywater coming from showers, a Membrane Bioreactor (MBR). The vertical-flow pilot scale-wetlands (VFCWs) consist of three polyethylene (PE) cylinders (RicionTerra, Germany) having the same dimensions (inner diameter 1.3 m, height 1 m with resulting surface area 1.3 m²) and set up to investigate the suitability of VF-CW for water reuse via the removal of macropollutants and pathogens from light greywater used as influent (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Sampling points of the pilot plant: raw light greywater (RW) inside the shelf; raw water collected from the pipe (PRW) and pumped to the existing Membrane Bioreactor, MBR; raw water influent (PDW) and effluent (FIW) of the drum filter; effluents from the vertical flow wetlands (CWE1, CWE2 and CWE3)

The VFCWs are successively filled, from the bottom to the top, with a 15 cm layer of expanded clay as drainage (2-8 mm), 75 cm of packing substrate and again 10 cm of expanded clay (2-8 mm). The modular treatment is supported by an innovative substrate whose efficiency is enhanced with the use of an admixture produced in a circular economy perspective (i.e. biochar from plants biologically activated), which was selected on the base of a preliminary study conducted at a laboratory scale under controlled conditions (Muniz Sacco et al., 2024). The substrate is composed of 85 % sand (Liapor, Germany) mixed with 15 % biochar produced from plant residues (Palaterra, Germany) biologically activated by fermentation.

Two wetlands are planted as following: *Carex + Iris pseudacorus* (VFCW1) and *Phragmites australis + Iris pseudacorus* (VFCW3) while VFCW2 remained unplanted. The choice of plants considers those macrophytes commonly applied to wetland configurations combining long and short roots which are beneficial for the aeration of the entire filter bed and to improve biodiversity. The wetlands are fed simultaneously, in downflow mode, via the use of three submersible pumps at the same flow rate, with the same greywater influent, which was previously pumped from a PE container suspended to the existing greywater collection shaft to avoid contamination from the concrete walls, and then, pre-filtered by a drum filter (20 m³ h⁻¹ capacity) to remove hair and fibres. The influent greywater is pumped at a Hydraulic Loading Rate (HLR) of 75 L d⁻¹m⁻² for 45 sec, 3

times per day (10 a.m., 6 p.m. and 2 a.m., according to the school calendar). To ensure photodegradation and healthy macrophytes development, UV lamps are installed to provide 8 hours per day of light (between 10 a.m. to 18 p.m.). The VFCWs are monitored weekly (see Figure 1, for sampling locations) to: i) characterize the composition of light raw grey water (RW); ii) evaluate the representativeness of a grab sample collected before the drum filter (PDW) with respect to the raw water and the water directed to the existing facility treating light greywater (PRW); iii) assess the performance of the drum filter and the quality of the filtrated water (FIW) which is the influent on the wetlands via comparing with PDW; iv) assess the performance of intensified substrate for light grey water (i.e. use of activated biochar as admixture); v) compare the performance of planted/unplanted wetlands and/or the performance of *Carex* towards *Phragmites australis* which is known to be a monoculture invasive plant. Removal rates are assessed considering that effluent samples (CWEs) were collected and related to the influent (FIW) for the determination of their elimination in VFCWs.

Analytical methods

Water quality parameters

Common parameters were routinely monitored. COD, TN, PO₄-P, NH₄-N and NO₃-N were measured with Hach Lange cuvette tests while dissolved Total Carbon (DTC), Total Organic Carbon (DOC) and Inorganic Carbon (DIC) with a TOC analyzer (Shimadzu, B). Oxidation-reduction potential, pH and conductivity were measured with conventional WTW (Xylem, UK) probes. Ions such as Ca and Mg are analysed externally from the laboratory Agrolab, D.

Pathogen indicators

Samples from the influent and the effluent of VFCWs were also collected during the start-up period and will be monitored for the following year. Total coliforms and *E. coli* will be analyzed by using Colilert-18 kit (IDEXX Laboratories Inc., USA). These pathogenic indicators were selected in this study as they are defined in all existing guidelines and regulations for greywater reuse. The most probable number (MPN) was determined from counted positive wells using the Quanti-Tray MPN Table, that was provided by the manufacturer. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is analysed externally from Agrolab (Germany).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization of raw greywater (preliminary results)

The inlet concentrations monitored during the start-up period of the pilot plant are not in line with previous studies due to the unexpected low COD values, however consistent over the monitoring period.

Figure 2. Characterization of raw influent (a) (N#5) and representativeness of sampling point before the drum filter (b) (N#8).

Total COD values range between 20 and 40 mg L⁻¹ (Figure 2, a) but most of them are represented by inorganic carbon which is related to the presence of Ca⁺ and Mg⁺ ions.

When looking at the different sampling location for raw influent, it can be observed that the water values are consistent for all parameters except ammonia. An ammonification process seems to occur from the shelf with the freshest collected water to the entry of the drum filter, via the pipeline, although the total nitrogen does not seem to show important changes.

Performance of VFCWs

High removal rates have been observed (up to 90 % for COD, almost 100 % for NH₄-N and TP) independently from the wetland being planted or unplanted, and independently from the type of plant (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Removal efficiencies of VFCW1 towards VFCW3 (a) and VFCW1 towards VFCW2 (b) (N#8, volume of treated water, c.a. 9.6 m³ per wetland).

Preliminary results showed a satisfactory disinfection process achieved with the wetland only, by depicting the pathogenic indicators Coliforms and E. Coli's values below the limit of quantification (1 Most Probable Number / 100 mL). The testing of in-line UV disinfection is foreseen along the testing period if needed.

OUTLOOK

The pilot plant will be monitored over 15 months of operation and will serve as a case study for: Short term - introduce water reuse in public buildings (State-liable) before launching new regulations in Luxembourg (156 public schools, 111.882 students); Long term – introduce regulations for water reuse in household and private sector, introduce incentive funding, promote water reuse for agriculture purposes (local food) for any sources including wastewater effluents, river and rain.

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